

significantly less susceptibility to isolates of one species may be highly susceptible to another.

Three characteristics can distinguish the four species. *P. fuscovaginae* and *P. syringae* pv. *oryzicola* produce a fluorescent blue pigment on King's B medium; *P. avenae* and *P. glumae* do not. Within each pair, the ability to use arginine for growth distinguishes the species—*P. fuscovaginae* and *P. glumae* are positive and *P. syringae* pv. *oryzicola* and *P. avenae* are negative. *P. syringae* pv. *oryzicola* also can utilize sucrose, the others cannot. These characteristics suggest components of a simple culture medium on which the four species could be differentiated.

We prepared 3 differentiating media from this basal medium: Ayers et al mineral salts medium (NH₄H₂PO₄, 1.0 g; KCl, 0.2 g; MgSO₄ 7H₂O, 0.2 g; bromothymol blue (1.6% alcohol solution), 1.0 ml; distilled water to 11 and 12 g bacteriological agar (OXOID No. 1); pH adjusted to 7.2.

For the first differentiating medium, 1.0 g arginine was added by millipore filtration to the autoclave sterilized basal medium. For the second medium, 1.0 g arginine was added to the basal medium and then the whole was autoclaved. For the third medium, bromothymol blue was omitted from the basal medium and 1.0 g arginine added by millipore filtration. Virulent isolates of 30 *P. avenae*, 88 *P. fuscovaginae*, 10 *P. syringae*, and 6 *P. glumae* were streaked onto the different media; growth and fluorescence under black light were evaluated at 24 h. Approximately 1 ml 1.5% sucrose solution was added to plates where isolates showed no growth after 48 h and growth and fluorescence checked again after 24 h.

Only the medium with bromothymol blue and arginine added by filtration distinguished the isolates. The results are presented in the table.

Growth plus fluorescence indicated *P. fuscovaginae*; growth with no fluorescence indicated *P. glumae*; no growth for 48 h but growth following addition of sucrose indicated *P. syringae* pv. *oryzicola*; no growth following addition of sucrose indicated *P. avenae*.

Differential reactions^a of 4 *Pseudomonas* spp. on medium with bromthymol and arginine (prepared by filtration).

Species	Arginine medium		Sucrose added ^b	
	Growth	Fluorescence	Growth	Fluorescence
<i>P. avenae</i>	—	...	—	...
<i>P. glumae</i>	+	—
<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	+	+
<i>P. syringae</i> pv. <i>oryzicola</i>	—	...	+	+

^a— = negative reaction, + = positive reaction, ... = not applicable. ^b1 ml sucrose added only if no growth was observed after 48 h.

The isolates identified using this medium must be pure, and their origins from rice and their pathogenicity on rice certain. The agar used must be bacteriological grade. Since whether or

not the pathogen produces fluorescent pigment on King's B medium will be known prior to using the arginine medium, detecting fluorescence on this medium is not essential. □

Early rice blast (BI) outbreak in Nepal

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BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*, is an important disease in rainy season (Jul-Nov) rice in Nepal but has not been reported in the endemic form in the pre-rainy season (Mar-Jul). A BI disease survey was made in rice plots of the experimental farm and adjoining

farmers' fields in Jhapa district (eastern BI-prone area) 13 May 1988 and 7 Jul 1988. Percent diseased leaf area was estimated on 100 randomly selected tillers per seedbed or per transplanted field.

Disease severity varied at seedling, maximum tillering, and dough stages (see table). Seedlings in Pusa-2-21 seedbeds were completely killed, and transplanted plants were heavily damaged by leaf and neck BI. This variety had been grown in this area for

BI disease severity in early rice of Nepal, 1988.

Field ^a	Date	Variety	Growth stage ^b	BI severity (%)	
				Leaf ^c	Neck ^d
<i>Jhapa</i>					
KAF	13 May	Pusa 2-21	1	100	—
KAF	13 May	Pusa 2-21	3	24	—
KAF	13 May	Pusa 2-21	3	33	—
KAF	13 May	Kankai 1	1	45	—
KAF	13 May	Kankai 1	3	12	—
KAF	7 Jul	Pusa 2-21	8	18	52
KAF	7 Jul	Pusa 2-21	8	20	68
KAF	7 Jul	Kankai 1	8	3	12
FF1	7 Jul	Pusa 2-21	8	16	48
FF2	7 Jul	Kankai 1	8	2	13
FF3	7 Jul	Kankai 1	8	2	21
<i>Chitwan</i>					
FF1	9 Jun	CH45	8	<1	7
FF2	9 Jun	CH45	8	2	8
FF3	9 Jun	CH45	8	<1	3
FF4	9 Jun	CH45	8	2	13
FF5	9 Jun	CH45	8	<1	5

^aKAF = Kankai Agricultural Farm, FF = farmer's field. ^bGrowth stages based on Standard evaluation system for rice scale of 0-9: 1 = seedling or transplanting, 3 = stem elongation, 8 = dough stage. ^cBased on rating scale of 0 (0%) to 10 (100%) on 100 randomly selected tillers/field. ^dBased on, number of rotten panicle neck on 100 tillers randomly selected.